

ISic000639

I.Sicily inscription 000639

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

brick

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Francesca Prado,system

Autopsy

None

Last Change

2021-07-02 - Francesca Prado tagged named entities and added English and Italian translation

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Original discovery not recorded.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 30 cm

Width 26 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Λείβερτε

2. χρηστέ

3. χάρε

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1994

Translation (en)

Farewell worthy Libertus!

Translation (it)

Addio, degno Libertus!

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644881

EDR 141109

EDCS 64800566

PHI 332877

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic000639>

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Bibliography

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